

University of Venda

Unstructured data collection tool

Nursing professionals (Maternal ART and PMTCT Services)

The interview guide is designed to gather in-depth insights into the complexities of maternal ART adherence and its impact on mother-to-child transmission of HIV. The guide consists of two sections, with demographics as the first section, followed by section two, consisting of central questions aimed at exploring nursing professionals' perspectives on maternal non-adherence to ART and its management in clinics. It is intended for use with nursing professionals overseeing PMTCT services in the Capricorn District.

Section A: Demographic information

Age:

Gender:

Highest professional qualification:

Years of experience in healthcare:

Current position:

Years in current role:

Facility type (clinic, CHC, district hospital, etc.):

Location of facility (urban/rural):

Section B: Central interview question

From your perspective, how would you describe the issue of maternal non-adherence to ART at your facility?